

PTSD Thought of as a Dislocated Joint: Qualitative Review

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Background: Opportunity exists to take up Levine's Theory on psychotrauma¹, building for 'a release of residual energy of the psychotrauma' a more exact theory that focuses on what causes this release. Levine uses Freud's theory: a fix of a breach in the protective barrier against stimuli. Before, with the breach, an explosive rushing out of life-energy creates a psychotrauma vortex.

Methods: Qualitative review by one reviewer by image searching a clip from the documentary Dream School² which shows a release of residual energy of the trauma.

Results: The clip looked analogical to the reposition of a shoulder. In PTSD, it might be the ontic-ontological joint that was repositioned. The function of the ontic-ontological joint was the ontological differentiation.³ It measured if the beings survival was threatened or not. In other words, if the being's beingness was false or true.³ The joint was the most fundamental joint in the network of willattitude.³

Conclusions: The result changes the trend of a breach. The result continues some of the trend of Dual Representation Theory⁴: that psychotrauma is a balance shift so that sensation-near images are strongly encoded while contextualized representations are weakened. However, in Dual Representation Theory it is the episodic memory which encoding is weakened while in the result it is the ontological memory. Levine's theory shows balancing too: he aligns a healing vortex to the psychotrauma vortex. He does this prior to renegotiating. Future research could be on if reposition is a step prior to the step reprocessing. Furthermore, it could be on the joint: if it is a muscle which becomes overloaded or an electricity group which becomes overloaded. Levine explains psychotrauma as a nervous system circuit breaker.

References

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